

Room Temperature Reactions of Freshly Formed Strontia with Moisture and CO₂

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Pure strontium oxide was required for a separate study and hence a routine characterization by room temperature X-ray diffraction was undertaken of the product obtained by the decomposition of strontium carbonate at 1150°. Surprisingly, the product after either air quenching or slow cooling to room temperature yielded an X-ray pattern different from that of either SrO or that of other strontium compounds listed in the ASTM X-ray data file.

In this study, it has been shown that cubic strontium oxide is formed at 1150° by the decomposition of either strontium carbonate or oxalate, but on cooling in air to room temperature ($T < 50^\circ$) it absorbs moisture very readily to form a crystalline Sr(OH)₂ [$a = 7.25$ Å; $c = 6.66$ Å] which gives the sharp X-ray pattern observed. This hydroxide picks up further moisture to form Sr(OH)₂.8H₂O which absorbs CO₂ and gets finally converted to SrCO₃. In the absence of moisture, absorption of CO₂ could not be detected at room temperature. However, in the range 400°--500° both SrO and Sr(OH)₂ absorb CO₂.

Pure strontium oxide was required for evaluating its high temperature vapourization behaviour. It was therefore decided to prepare the oxide by the decomposition of strontium carbonate (taken as such or formed by the *insitu* decomposition of the oxalate) and routinely characterize the product by standard X-ray diffraction techniques. However, when the X-ray pattern of the decomposition product was obtained, it was found that the sharp X-ray diffraction pattern did not correspond to that of SrO or of any other strontium compound listed in the ASTM X-ray data file.

It is known that it is difficult to prepare crystalline strontium oxide by decomposition of the salts at low temperatures and that very high temperatures (close to the m.p.) are required to form the crystalline oxide¹; that depending on the salt decomposed and the temperature, cubic or other forms of SrO could be obtained²; that SrO rapidly absorbs CO₂ at 550°* and presence of water helps the uptake of CO₂ and that Sr(OH)₂ is obtained by the action of water on strontia³, yet none of these facts as also the recent work of Copeland and Swalin⁴ on the formation of strontium oxide hydrate could explain the strange observation.

Hence the present study was undertaken to identify and characterize the products obtained on cooling strontium oxide formed by the decomposition of the carbonate to room temperature and on further exposure to ambient atmosphere.

* All temperatures are reported in degrees Celsius.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : SrO was obtained from SrCO₃ or SrC₂O₄.H₂O which in turn was prepared by the co-precipitation of a solution of SrCl₂.6H₂O and either (NH₄)₂CO₃ or (NH₄)₂C₂O₄. All chemicals were of BDH "Analar" grade.

T.G.-D.T.A.: High temperature Stanton thermobalance (sensitivity 1 mg) with D.T.A. attachment⁵ was used for simultaneous recording of T.G. and D.T.A. curves. A uniform heating rate of 6°/min was used and the reference material was pure Al₂O₃ calcined at 1300°.

X-ray Analysis : Standard photographic and diffractometric techniques were used.

Gas Analysis : The gases evolved during the various reactions (as indicated in T.G.A.) were analysed for H₂O and CO₂ by standard gas absorption technique.

Infra-red studies : Infra-red spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 237 spectrometer using Nujol mull technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Formation of SrO : The fact that cubic strontium oxide is formed at temperatures greater than 1050° by the decomposition of strontium carbonate (either taken as such or formed *in situ* by the decomposition of strontium oxalate) was undisputably established by T.G.A. (Table 1). Nevertheless when this SrO is cooled to room temperature either slowly

TABLE 1

Heating rate = 6°/min. Weight of SrC₂O₄.H₂O taken = 400 mg

Reaction	Theoretical loss	Thermogram 1	Thermogram 2
SrC ₂ O ₄ .H ₂ O			
↓ -H ₂ O	37.1 mg	37.0 mg (150°—200°)	37.0 mg (140°—200°)
SrC ₂ O ₄	57.7 mg	58.0 mg	58.0 mg
↓ -CO		(380°—500°)	(400°—500°)
SrCO ₃	90.7 mg	90.0 mg	89.5 mg
↓ -CO ₂		(860°—1110°)	(860°—1140°)
SrO			

Table 1. The theoretical and observed weight loss during the thermal decomposition of SrC₂O₄.H₂O leading to the eventual formation of SrO.

in the thermobalance or rapidly by air-quenching, the product obtained was undoubtedly different as can be seen from the X-ray powder pattern (Table 2). This pattern could not be identified with that of any of the strontium compounds listed in the ASTM X-ray data card file.

TABLE 2

Material obtained imme- diately after cooling of SrO	SrO desiccated over Mg(ClO ₄) ₂ for 16 days	SrO exposed to atmosphere for 4 days	SrO exposed to atmos- phere for 14 days	Prepared SrCO ₃	ASTM SrO	ASTM Sr(OH) ₂ 8H ₂ O	ASTM SrO ₂ 8H ₂ O	ASTM SrO ₂	ASTM SrO 9H ₂ O	ASTM SrCO ₃
6.24 ⁽⁵⁰⁾	6.25 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	6.34 ⁽²⁰⁾ 5.74 ⁽²⁰⁾				6.40 ⁽⁴⁰⁾ 5.80 ⁽⁴⁰⁾	6.33 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		5.68 ⁽⁵⁰⁾	
4.56 ⁽⁵⁵⁾	4.56 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	4.48 ⁽¹⁵⁾ 4.27 ⁽²⁵⁾	4.35 ⁽⁵⁾ 4.15 ⁽⁵⁾ 3.90 ⁽³⁰⁾	4.39 ⁽⁵⁾ 4.19 ⁽⁵⁾ 3.92 ⁽²⁵⁾		4.51 ⁽⁴⁰⁾ 4.29 ⁽⁶⁷⁾	4.48 ⁽⁶⁰⁾ 4.19 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		4.31 ⁽⁷⁰⁾	4.37 ⁽¹⁴⁾ 4.21 ⁽⁶⁾
3.64 ⁽²⁵⁾	3.65 ⁽³⁰⁾	3.54 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ 3.48 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	3.55 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ 3.47 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	3.54 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ 3.46 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		3.54 ⁽⁵³⁾ 3.19 ⁽⁷⁾	3.50 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾		3.31 ⁽⁷⁰⁾	3.54 ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾ 3.45 ⁽⁷⁰⁾
3.34 ⁽³⁰⁾	3.35 ⁽³⁰⁾									
3.14 ⁽²⁵⁾	3.13 ⁽³⁰⁾	3.00 ⁽¹⁵⁾	3.00 ⁽²⁵⁾ 2.85 ⁽²⁰⁾	3.01 ⁽²⁰⁾ 2.83 ⁽²⁰⁾	2.98 ⁽⁹⁰⁾		3.17 ⁽⁴⁰⁾	3.14 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾	3.16 ⁽⁵⁰⁾	3.01 ⁽²²⁾ 2.86 ⁽⁵⁾ 2.84 ⁽²⁰⁾
2.82 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.82 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.78 ⁽²⁰⁾ 2.62 ⁽¹⁵⁾	2.73 ⁽²⁰⁾	2.73 ⁽²⁰⁾		2.76 ⁽⁶⁷⁾ 2.74 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.75 ⁽⁶⁰⁾ 2.63 ⁽²⁰⁾		2.62 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.60 ⁽¹²⁾
		2.54 ⁽²⁵⁾	2.53 ⁽¹⁰⁾	2.54 ⁽¹⁰⁾	2.58 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾		2.56 ⁽⁴⁰⁾ 2.54 ⁽⁵³⁾ 2.53 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		2.52 ⁽⁹⁶⁾	2.55 ⁽²³⁾
2.46 ⁽⁴⁵⁾	2.47 ⁽⁴⁵⁾	2.46 ⁽⁴⁰⁾	2.46 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.47 ⁽⁶⁵⁾		2.43 ⁽²⁷⁾				2.48 ⁽³⁴⁾ 2.46 ⁽⁴⁰⁾ 2.45 ⁽³³⁾
2.29 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.29 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	2.29 ⁽¹⁰⁾	2.26 ⁽¹⁵⁾	2.27 ⁽¹⁰⁾		2.28 ⁽²⁷⁾	2.26 ⁽⁴⁰⁾			2.27 ⁽⁵⁾
2.22 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾	2.23 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾		2.18 ⁽¹⁵⁾	2.18 ⁽¹⁰⁾			2.24 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		2.24 ⁽⁷⁰⁾	
2.10 ⁽¹⁵⁾	2.10 ⁽¹⁵⁾		2.11 ⁽¹⁰⁾	2.11 ⁽¹⁰⁾		2.14 ⁽¹³⁾	2.096 ⁽⁶⁰⁾		2.10 ⁽⁵⁰⁾	2.18 ⁽¹⁶⁾ 2.10 ⁽⁷⁾ 2.05 ⁽⁵⁰⁾
		2.04 ⁽³⁵⁾	2.05 ⁽³⁵⁾ 2.01 ⁽¹⁰⁾	2.05 ⁽⁴⁰⁾ 2.01 ⁽⁵⁾		2.02 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾		2.01 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾	2.01 ⁽⁵⁵⁾	2.01 ⁽¹⁰⁰⁾
1.97 ⁽¹⁵⁾	1.97 ⁽¹⁵⁾		1.98 ⁽¹⁰⁾ 1.93 ⁽¹⁰⁾	1.98 ⁽¹⁰⁾ 1.94 ⁽¹⁰⁾						1.99 ⁽²⁶⁾ 1.95 ⁽²¹⁾
		1.90 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.90 ⁽²⁵⁾	1.90 ⁽³⁰⁾		1.89 ⁽¹³⁾	1.89 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	1.88 ⁽⁴⁹⁾	1.89 ⁽⁷⁰⁾	1.91 ⁽³⁵⁾
1.82 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.82 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.82 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.82 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.82 ⁽³⁰⁾	1.83 ⁽⁸⁰⁾					1.83 ⁽³¹⁾ 1.81 ⁽¹⁶⁾

Table 2. Comparison of the *d*-spacings of the different products obtained on cooling and exposure of SrO and the standard ASTM X-ray patterns.

Characterization of product obtained on cooling : The identification and characterization of the intermediate and end products formed as the freshly formed SrO is cooled to room temperature and exposed to ambient atmosphere were attempted using the various techniques mentioned.

1. *Product formed on cooling to room temperature* : T.G.A. showed that 400 mg of SrCO_3 yield 280.7 mg* of SrO at 1150° . No further weight change was observed upto 1300° . The power to the furnace was then switched off and the weight changes recorded as the sample cooled.

The main features of the cooling curve are :

(i) small weight loss of about 2 mg in the range 1300° to 500° ; (ii) a gain of 4 mg between 500° – 400° followed by a very gradual and small weight gain of about 1mg upto 300° ; (iii) no weight change from 300° to 50° ; (iv) uniform weight gain at the rate of 3.6 mg/hr for the next nearly twelve hours, after which the experiments were terminated.

Total weight gained in this interval—42 mg. [As shown in separate experiments at room temperature and in ambient environment the weight gain continues for several days.]

When the sample was reheated, a small gain in weight (2 mg) occurred between 300° to 500° (just as was observed during cooling) followed by a sudden loss of 45 mg between 500° to 650° . This loss corresponded to the entire weight gained (44 mg) in the cooling (from 300°) and reheat cycle. No weight change occurred between 650° and 800° .

Fig. 1. D.T.A. & T.G.A. curves of—

- (a) $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ prepared separately and exposed for a few hours.
- (b) Air quenched SrO.

* These weights and weight changes are from a typical run with the sample in a narrow (10 mm dia, 15 mm ht.) platinum crucible and are mentioned as an indication of the processes taking place. The extent of these weight changes will vary with the experimental set up, the geometry of the sample holder, etc. This is expected to be more severe in the present case since it involves not only gas adsorption reaction, but because these reactions occur simultaneously.

Since on reheating no weight change was observed upto 300° , it is concluded that the product is not a hydrate as suggested by Swalin and Copeland⁴. The facts that (a) the entire weight loss occurred between 500° and 650° where as shown by a separate experiment, only the $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ decomposes, and (b) the D.T.A. peaks observed in this range match those observed during the decomposition of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ [Fig. 1], establish that the product formed is $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$, and that neither the oxide remains as such nor a hydroxide hydrate is formed immediately on cooling below 300° .

The small weight gain observed during the initial cooling in the range 500° to 400° is in conformity with the earlier observation that CO_2 is picked up by the oxide at about 550° .³ While quantitative correlations of the weight changes are difficult because the rate of pick-up of moisture and CO_2 depends on the exposed area, the amount of sample, packing characteristics, relative humidity, etc., yet these afford some support. 280.7 mg of SrO, if converted to $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ should show a weight gain of 48.8 mg. However, if the 4 mg weight gain between 500° and 400° is attributed to formation of SrCO_3 , it would account for 9.4 mg SrO. Thus only 271.3 mg of unreacted SrO would be left. This amount if converted to the $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ should give a weight gain of 47.1 mg which is in reasonable agreement with the observed weight gain of 42 mg, especially since the experiment was arbitrarily terminated after 12 hrs. The existence of small amount of carbonate is shown from the small loss beyond 900° .

The small gain in weight observed when the product, which is essentially $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$, is reheated must also be attributed to pick up of CO_2 . In this case, however, no carbonate is formed but possibly a loose complex like $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2$. This is inferred from the facts that (a) the 45 mg weight loss observed between 500° – 650° is, within experimental error, equal to the sum of weight gained at room temperature (42 mg) and the weight gained between 400° – 500° on reheating (2 mg), and (b) the D.T.A. curve during the decomposition is very complex and shows at least four peaks, indicating that it is not a simple dehydroxylation reaction.

It can therefore be concluded that the initial product formed on cooling to room temperature is essentially strontium hydroxide with very little strontium carbonate formed during cooling in the range 500° to 300° . The amount of this carbonate would depend upon the time taken by the SrO sample to cool through this range, the gas-solid interface area, the amount of the sample, packing, relative humidity, atmospheric concentration of CO_2 , etc.

One of the most unusual aspects was provided by the X-ray study of the product. The reason for initiating the present study was the observation that the X-ray pattern of the product obtained on cooling did not correspond to either that of SrO or of any other known strontium compounds. To quench the SrO formed at 1150° the thermobalance furnace was lifted and the sample was taken from the crucible, crushed and mounted in the X-ray powder camera. These operations were completed in less than 2 minutes and the photograph taken with an exposure of 2 hours, yet the powder pattern obtained is identical with that obtained when SrO is slowly cooled to room temperature (Table 2). This fact proves that the product obtained on cooling, which has been identified as $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$, is

highly crystalline. It is most unusual that the adsorption of moisture at room temperature should lead to the formation of crystalline $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ and that too in such a short time. This pattern of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ could be indexed on the basis of a hexagonal unit cell with $a = 7.25 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.66 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 3).

TABLE 3

Indexed powder pattern of the material obtained on quenching SrO in air

d_{observed}	d_{computed}	$I/I_{100}\%$	Index
6.24	6.28	50	100
4.56	4.57	55	101
3.64	3.63	25	110
3.34	3.33	30	002
3.14	3.14	25	200
2.82	2.84	60	201
2.46	2.45	45	112
2.29	2.29	80	202
2.22	2.22	100	003
2.10	2.09	15	300
1.97	2.00	15	301
1.82	1.81	30	220
1.75	1.75	10	221
1.69	1.69	10	311
1.62	1.62	15	213
1.53	1.53	15	401
1.48	1.47	5	204
1.42	1.42	5	402
1.40	1.40	5	223
1.38	1.37	5	410
1.34	1.34	5	411
1.31	1.30	5	304
1.29	1.28	5	403
1.27	1.27	5	412
1.23	1.23	10	501
1.17	1.17	10	421

Table 3. Indexed X-ray powder pattern of the material obtained on quenching SrO in air, considered to be $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$.

2. *Products obtained on prolonged exposure at room temperature*: Since T.G. studies indicated that the gain in weight was continuing even after about 12 hours exposure at room temperature, the quantitative uptake of H_2O and/or CO_2 on prolonged exposure was studied separately.

1 gm samples of strontium oxalate (equivalent of 535 mg SrO) were heated in two platinum crucibles** upto 1150° in an electric muffle furnace and then air quenched. One crucible was immediately kept in a desiccator over magnesium perchlorate, while the other was exposed to normal room atmosphere. Weight changes in both these samples were followed for several days. T.G., effluent gas, infra-red and X-ray analyses were also made of the products after different time intervals. For these latter studies, separate samples of the oxalate were treated and exposed in an identical manner.

As may be seen from Table 4, the oxide exposed to air gained 284.6 mg (50% of the weight of SrO) in the first 42 hrs and 35.2 mg in the next 54 hrs. The rate of weight gain progressively decreased and at the end of six days, the total gain was 334 mg. After this period there was a slow loss in weight, and 40 mg weight loss was observed over the next six days; the rate of weight loss increasing with time.

TABLE 4

Time of exposure (hours)		Weight gained or lost	
Total	additional	Exposed SrO	Desiccated SrO
42		+0.2846 gm	+0.0139 gm
96	54	+0.0352	+0.0085
120	24	+0.0086	+0.0075
144	24	+0.0056	+0.0107
168	24	-0.0010	+0.0060
192	24	-0.0050	+0.0068
264	72	-0.0340	+0.0082

Table 4. Observed weight changes on prolonged exposure of SrO at room temperature in air and in desiccator.

In contrast the sample kept in the desiccator hardly gained in weight. Even the eight to ten milligram weight gain shown in Table 4 was actually observed during the weighing operation, when the sample had to be exposed to ambient atmosphere. The total gain in weight was only 60 mg after 10 days and there was no weight loss as observed in the sample exposed to normal room atmosphere.

These results clearly demonstrate that the large gain in weight is due to pick-up of moisture and not CO_2 . Further this large gain in weight corresponds to the eventual formation of hydroxide hydrate. The gradual diminishing of the rate of weight gain due to moisture pick-up and the eventual increasing rate of weight loss are due to gradual formation of $SrCO_3$ from the strontium hydroxide hydrate.

** Prolonged heating of SrO in platinum crucibles at these high temperatures should not be done, as it was found that the crucible is attacked.

This was confirmed by a T.G.-D.T.A. and E.G.A. study of the products formed. For the T.G.-D.T.A. studies, 400 mg of SrCO_3 (equivalent to 280.76 gm SrO) were heated and the products formed after exposing to ambient atmosphere for different periods were analysed. For comparison, the products from a sample of SrO kept over magnesium perchlorate were also analysed. The results are shown in fig. 2 and Table 5. The results of E.G.A. of SrO exposed for about 48 hours and given in Table 6.

TABLE 5

Size of platinum crucible used for T.G.A.	History of SrO sample	Approximate time (hours) of exposure to conditions in prev. col.	Weight loss upto 250° (water of hydration)	Weight loss between 500°-700° (hydroxide H_2O)	Weight loss above 850° (CO_2)	Corresponds to mg of total SrO	Theoretically calculated amount of total SrO (mg)
Big (dia = 18 mm) (h = 24 mm)	Exposed to atmosphere	17	145 mg	42 mg	8.5 mg	261.81	343.00
	-do-	162	169 mg	25 mg	50 mg	261.68	
	-do-	240	—	1 mg	113 mg	271.90	
	Desiccated over $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	378	—	56 mg	4 mg	331.81	
Small (dia = 10mm) (h = 15 mm)	Partially decomposed SrCO_3 (heated upto 1000°)	20	6 mg	5 mg	106.5 mg	280.76	280.76
	Exposed to atmosphere	17	8 mg	47 mg	4.5 mg	281.18	

Table 5. Summary of the weight losses in different temperature ranges observed during T.G.A. of SrO exposed under different conditions.

TABLE 6

Temperature range	% of total weight of sample lost in the form of	
	H_2O	CO_2
25°— 250°	5.86	—
250°— 450°	4.82	—
450°— 550°	0.41	—
550°— 750°	—	—
750°— 850°	—	0.95
850°—1300°	—	0.59

Table 6. Effluent gas analysis of SrO exposed for about 48 hours in air at room temperature.

From Table 5 it is obvious that progressively (a) the amount of H_2O which is lost upto 250° as the hydrate increases, (b) the amount of CO_2 lost from the carbonate in the range 900° to 1100° also increases and (c) the amount of H_2O lost as the hydroxide in the range 500° to 650° diminishes.

In comparison the sample kept in the dessicator showed no loss upto 300° . Almost the entire weight gained was lost between 500° to 650° due to dehydroxylation and only 4 mg lost in the region of carbonate decomposition.

This clearly proves that the freshly formed SrO picks up moisture to first form the hydroxide which is nearly complete in 10 to 12 hours; the hydroxide hydrate is formed in about 1 day and this hydrate picks up CO_2 to eventually form the strontium carbonate. Infra-red study supports this conclusion since in the air-quenched "SrO", no bands due to CO_3 were observed. Weak bands due to CO_3 appeared in samples exposed for a few hours. Because these processes are occurring simultaneously it was not possible to uniquely establish the composition of the hydrate but from X-ray studies it is considered to be $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ since there is close similarity with the standard ASTM pattern (Table 2).

It is significant that in the absence of moisture, there is no pick-up of CO_2 and further even the hydroxide does not pick up CO_2 . It is only when the hydrate is formed that CO_2 is absorbed. This can be seen by comparing the T.G.-D.T.A. curves of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (which was especially prepared and exposed to air for a few hours). [Cf. fig. 1(a) & 2].

Fig. 2. Comparison of the T.G. curves of air quenched SrO exposed for different time intervals in air and in a desiccator with that of pure SrCO_3 .

Some unusual features : Certain peculiarities which have been observed in this study are stated for record. Explanation is still sought for these.

(1) When the air quenched "SrO" is immediately reheated in the thermobalance it shows a *gain* in weight in the region 250° – 500° . Yet the D.T.A. shows an endotherm.

(2) This weight gain is immediately followed by a weight loss in the region 500° – 650° . This loss equals the sum of the weight gained by the sample at room temperature and the weight gained as at (1) above.

(3) This weight loss between 500° – 650° corresponds to dehydroxilation of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$, yet the D.T.A. curve shows a complex set of endotherms. At least four well characterized peaks can be identified (fig. 1) which were also observed in the D.T.A. of the freshly prepared $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Conclusion : While as noted above there are still some unanswered questions, from the present study it can be concluded that freshly formed SrO on cooling picks up small amounts of CO_2 in the range 500° to 400° and on cooling to room temperature rapidly absorbs moisture to form a crystalline $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$, which picks up further moisture to form a hydrated hydroxide (most probably $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$) which picks up CO_2 to eventually form SrCO_3 .

If the hydrated hydroxide is not formed, carbon dioxide is not absorbed.

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